

Quantum Mechanics and the Multiverse Hypothesis: Exploring the Evidential Landscape

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Abstract

While quantum mechanics can provide evidence for the existence of a multiverse, it does not prove that multiverses exist. 6 theories (**MWI, Inflationary Multiverse, Copenhagen interpretation, Quantum Entanglement, Quantum Computing and String Theory**) are analyzed and presented (with their respective problems) to the reader in an objective manner so that they can draw their own conclusions as to whether or not they believe in the existence of the multiverse. However, something to keep in mind is that through the development of new technologies, these theories can become testable in a large scale manner, and thus, conclusive evidence for the existence of the multiverse can possibly arise.

Keywords: Evidence, Multiverse, Quantum Mechanics, Theory, Technology.

Introduction

Is the multiverse real? This is a question that researchers have been trying to find an answer to for decades, but there still isn't any definitive answer.

The multiverse is a theoretical concept that suggests our universe may be just one of many, or perhaps an infinite number of universes, existing simultaneously. There are a plethora of theories which promise to provide evidence for the existence of the multiverse; but are they correct?

This paper will analyze 6 of these theories to find evidence for the existence of the supposed multiverse. This paper will highlight what evidence is provided by each theory as well as what they propose, and discuss what problems arise with each corresponding theory. These will all be laid out in an objective manner, as the goal of this paper is to allow the reader to understand the

essence, evidence, and problems of each theory in order to make their own judgement about whether or not they think quantum mechanics can provide evidence for the existence of a multiverse.

Literature Review

There are several theories in the realm of quantum mechanics that promise to provide evidence for the existence of the multiverse:

1) The Many Worlds Interpretation (MWI)

The Many-Worlds Interpretation (MWI) in quantum mechanics suggests that there are infinite parallel universes at the same time and space as our own. Each time a decision is made, the universe splits into all the possible outcomes that could arise from the decision (decohesion). This theory suggests that just because we only detect one solution to the wave function, it doesn't necessarily mean alternative solutions do not exist. The theory also suggests that time doesn't exist in a coherent, linear motion but moves in jumps and starts. The MWI consists of two parts:

1. A theory that yields the time evolution of the quantum state of the (single) Universe.
2. A prescription which sets up a correspondence between the quantum state of the Universe and our experiences

This theory has both its merits and its limitations. Part (1) states that the ontology of the universe is a quantum state, which evolves according to the Schrödinger equation or its relativistic generalization. It is a rigorous mathematical theory and is not problematic philosophically. Part (2) involves “our experiences” which do not have a rigorous definition. An additional difficulty in setting up (2) follows from the fact that human languages were developed at a time when people did not suspect the existence of parallel worlds. The very nature of this theory suggests that there are infinite universes that stem from every single decision made; calculating such outcomes to provide a definitive answer to whether or not this theory is correct requires calculations that are beyond the scope of the technology we possess in the present.

However, the problem with this theory is that quantum states collapse under observation. Additionally, the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle states that there's a fundamental limit to how precisely certain pairs of physical properties of a particle can be known simultaneously. The theory also does not outline specific parameters to what constitutes a measurement

4) Quantum Entanglement

When two particles become entangled, their states become linked, meaning the state of one particle instantly influences the state of the other, regardless of the distance between them. This connection remains even if the particles are separated by vast distances. **Quantum entanglement** suggests that if you measure the state of one entangled particle, you instantly know the state of the other particle, even if it's light-years away which can be evidence of the multiverse.

This phenomenon claims that the state of one particle can be determined by analyzing its entangled pair, no matter how far apart they are. Such an effect contradicts classical physics and led Albert Einstein himself to call it *“spooky action at a distance.”*

5) Quantum Computing

In a **quantum computer**, qubits (quantum bits) can exist in a superposition of states, allowing the computer to explore multiple possibilities simultaneously. Some researchers have suggested that quantum computers might be interacting with parallel universes as they perform calculations. When a quantum computer performs a computation, it simultaneously processes information in multiple parallel universes. Each computation takes place in a distinct branch of reality, and the quantum computer effectively leverages this multiplicity to solve problems that are impossible for classical computers. Although quantum computers are still in their early stages of development, they have already demonstrated several amazing and mind boggling phenomena.

For example, in 2022, researchers from Google used a mere nine entangled qubits to perform an experimental demonstration of a traversable wormhole. Google's latest quantum computer chip, which the team dubbed Willow, has ignited a heated debate in the scientific community over the existence of parallel universes. Not to be outdone, experimenters from Singapore that same year managed to entangle two superconducting qubits held in high vacuum with a living tardigrade. The process of quantum computation could be seen as a way of exploring different branches of the multiverse, with the final result corresponding to the outcome in one particular universe. While this idea is speculative, it highlights the potential connections between quantum computing and the Many-Worlds Interpretation.

Quantum computing provides compelling evidence for the existence of the multiverse, but challenges with maintaining qubits, error correction, scalability, software development, and the overall cost of quantum hardware are all issues that future developments of quantum computing have to overcome before we can extract definitive information about the multiverse's existence.

(Credit: ResearchGate)

6) String Theory

String theory, a theoretical framework that attempts to unify all fundamental forces of nature, proposes that there are up to 11 dimensions. According to string theory, our universe could be one of many “branes” floating in higher-dimensional space. Each brane represents a different universe.

However, string theory has two large problems:

1. Lack of experimental verification methods.
2. The full theory does not have a satisfactory definition in all circumstances, especially regarding many phenomena of strong forces.

Conclusion

While quantum mechanics can provide compelling evidence for the existence of the multiverse (to an extent), the problems with each of these theories limits the scope of the believability in the existence of the multiverse. Broadly speaking, there are two main categories of problems that these theories face:

1. **Lack of testability**
2. **Lack of advanced technology**

All theories regarding the multiverse usually fall into one or both of these categories.

Additionally, (although this only applies to older theories) many theories have been steadily disproven as new discoveries about the universe have been made. Therefore, quantum mechanics cannot prove the existence of the multiverse.

However, technology is evolving rapidly, as we see with quantum computing, and scientists are constantly trying to find evidence for the multiverse. If new technology keeps being developed like it is at present, then at some point in the future, we may be able to test theories regarding the multiverse and give researchers the tools they need to find a conclusive answer to whether or not the multiverse exists.

So, while quantum mechanics cannot currently provide definitive evidence for the existence of a multiverse, as technology is improved, in the future it might be able to.

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